

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: HUBAIL****FIRST NAME: SALMAN****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the following software: MSWord 360 on Windows 11

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In the context of academic essays, as described by Cleenewerck, Laurent, and

Kabiru Gulma, what is the essential function of a “thesis statement”?

- To provide a detailed outline of every point discussed in the essay.
- To summarize the findings of the research conducted for the essay.
- To clearly and concisely answer the essay question and state the main argument.¹**
- To introduce the topic of the essay with a broad and general statement.

2. As stated by Cleenewerck, Laurant and Kabiru Gulma, which of the following

actions constitutes plagiarism?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 5th ed. (Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024), 41.

- Including a direct quote from a source and citing the author and page number.
 - Paraphrasing an author's ideas and expressing them in your own words with a citation.
 - Using the exact words of a source without enclosing them in quotation marks, even if the source is cited.²**
 - Referencing common knowledge that is widely available in multiple sources.
3. **The Turabian Rules of Style defines a "warrant" as the element of argument. What is the role of a "warrant" in constructing a research argument?**
- To present statistical data and factual evidence.
 - To state the main point or claim of the argument.
 - To acknowledge and respond to potential objections from readers.
 - To explain why the reasons provided are relevant to the claim being made.³**
4. **When should a quotation be formatted as a block quotation according to the Turabian Rules of Style?**
- When it is more than 30 words.
 - When it is more than 2 lines.
 - When it is more than 5 lines.⁴**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 34.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 3-4.

⁴ *Ibid.*, 75.

When it is more than 50 words.

5. **What is the most likely source of unintentional researcher bias explained in the Guide of Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research?**

Deliberate manipulation of data.

Lack of understanding of statistical methods.

Belief in the inherent relationship among variables.⁵

Failure to follow APA guidelines.

6. **Which of the following does JP Sampson identify in his Guide as an example of a limitation in the measures used in a dissertation?**

Difficulty in recruiting participants.

Low reliability of a measure in the study.⁶

Lack of random assignment to groups.

Failure to obtain IRB approval.

7. **Based on JP Sampson's Guide, which of the following is NOT a component of data analysis validity?**

Congruence.

Accuracy.

⁵ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 8.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 59.

- Reliability.
- Transparency**⁷

8. **The European Commission's Guide provides the standard format for citing CJEU judgments in footnotes. Which of the following is the correct way to cite a judgment from the Court of Justice of the European Union in a footnote?**

- Judgment of the Court of Justice of 12 July 2005, Schempp, C-403/03.
- Judgment of the Court of Justice of 12 July 2005, Schempp, C-403/03, ECLI:EU:C:2005:446.
- Judgment of the Court of Justice of 12 July 2005, Schempp, C-403/03, ECLI:EU:C:2005:446, paragraphs 22 to 24.
- Both 2 and 3 are correct.**⁸

9. **Based on the European Commission English Style Guide, which of the following is the correct way to cite the Treaty on European Union (TEU) in a legal text?**

- EU Treaty.
- Maastricht Treaty.
- Treaty on European Union.
- Both 1 and 2 are correct.

⁷ Sampson, 48.

⁸ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translator in the European Commission*, 8th ed. (European Commission, 2016), 88.

- All the above are correct.**⁹

10. **What is the correct way to refer to the European Central Bank (ECB) in a legal act?**

- European Central Bank (ECB).
- ECB.
- Central Bank.
- Both a and b are correct.**¹⁰

⁹ European Commission, 76.

¹⁰ Ibid., 92.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 5th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press, 2024.

European Commission, trans., *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. 8th ed. Brussels: European Commission, 2016.

Sampson, James P. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations, Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. FitzGerald, and the University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 9th ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.